

NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: March 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 [Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for March 2014

Highlights...

- Science@NASA brings us a fun clip about what it would be like to **drink a cup of coffee in space**;
- With an extension of support until at least 2024, the **International Space Station** is poised to make discoveries we can't even imagine today;
- Astronomers devised a new method for examining data from the Kepler telescope and NASA has recently announced the **discovery of over 700 new extrasolar planets**;
- Stephen Hawking said what?? SciShow tackles recent headlines declaring that **“there are no black holes”** and explain what Stephen Hawking might have actually meant; and
- Remember that large snow storm in early February? We have video of **winter storm Pax as seen from space**, from footage taken by the NOAA GOES-East satellite.

Archives

Select Month

Tags

ASTRONOMICAL PLATES

ASTRONOMY

ASTRONOMY THESIS COLLECTION

CFA BIBLIOGRAPHY

CFA HISTORY

CFA NEWS

CULTURAL ASTRONOMY SERIES

EVENTS

HISTORY

METADATA

METASAT

ORCID

PHAEDRA

UNIFIED ASTRONOMY THESAURUS

VISUAL ASTRONOMY DISPLAY

WOLBACH LIBRARY

ZOONIVERSE

ScienceCasts: The Zero Gravity Coffee Cup

[Playlist Archive](#) [Suggestions](#), [Comments](#), or [Questions](#)

Author Recent Posts

Katie Frey

Assistant Head Librarian at [Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian](#)

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

< CfA Bibliography for
February 2014

CfA Bibliography for
March 2014 >

Leave a Comment

Logged in as Hayley Curtis. [Edit your profile](#). [Log out?](#) Required fields are marked *

Comment*

Post Comment